

**NONLOCAL ANALYSIS OF EDGE-CRACKED NANOBEAMS
UNDER MODE I AND MIXED-MODE (I+II) STATIC LOADING**

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, the behaviour of an edge-cracked nanobeam under both Mode I and Mixed-Mode (I+II) static bending loading is analysed by using the Stress-Driven nonlocal Model (SDM), being the SDM applied for the first time in the case of Mixed-Mode loading. More precisely, the cracked nanobeam is modelled by using a modification of the classical cracked-beam theory, consisting in dividing the beam into two beam segments connected through a massless elastic rotational spring located at the cracked cross-section. The bending stiffness of the cracked cross-section is computed by exploiting: (i) the Griffith energy criterion and (ii) the conventional Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics. Cracks under both Mode I and Mixed-Mode (I+II) loading are considered. Finally, an edge-cracked cantilever nanobeam subjected to a transversal point load at the free end is analysed. The static deflection is calculated and discussed for different values of relative crack depth, crack location and crack orientation.

KEYWORDS: edge-crack, massless elastic spring, Mixed-Mode, nanobeam, Stress-Driven nonlocal Model, Stress-Intensity Factor

1. INTRODUCTION

With the recent development and miniaturisation of micro- and nano-electronical devices, due to the increasing demand for high density integration, such systems incorporate structural elements characterised by a micro- or a nano-scale length, such as sensors and actuators [1,2].

In the context of nano-scale length, such elements can be nanobeams, nanoplates, nanobars, nanorings, single-curved nanoshells and double-curved nanoshells [3]. In nanostructures, where the sizes are small and comparable to crystal or molecular distances, size effect in mechanical behaviour is detected, and it cannot be neglected when the behaviour analysis is performed. In such an investigation, classical continuum mechanics cannot be used, due to its scale-free character: rather, atomistic models and Generalised Continuum Theories (GCTs) have to be used. It is worth noticing that, since atomistic modelling is quite time consuming, size-dependent continuum mechanics approaches are widely employed to explain the size-dependent mechanical behaviour.

Lattice-based nonlocal models, Eringen's nonlocal models, gradient theory of elasticity, strain- and stress-driven nonlocal models, and peridynamic theory are some of the most widely known and accepted GCTs [4,5].

In the context of the stress-driven nonlocal model, that is the GCT employed in the present research work, it has been successfully applied to solve numerous engineering problems, such as: static bending behaviour [6-11], buckling [12,13] and free transverse vibrations [14-18] of nanobeams. It is important to highlight that the above cited papers refer to intact nanobeams.

Although the probability of the presence of defects in nanostructures is quite low, it could dramatically modify their mechanical behaviour and represent a fatal damage for the whole component. For example, in an electromechanical system, a single dislocation present in a structural element, can bring about a malfunction due to the lack of the electric current.

In the context of cracked nanostructures under static loading, that is, the loading condition examined in the present research work, both atomistic modelling [19-28] and GCTs [29-39] are put forward into several studies to investigate their fracture behaviour, being the experimental investigation still a challenge, due to technical difficulties connected with the nanoscale sizes involved.

Due to the fact that, to the best knowledge of the present authors, the Stress-Driven nonlocal Model has not been applied yet to edge-cracked nanobeams under Mixed-Mode (I+II) static loading (although longitudinal cracked nanobeams have been already investigated [37-39]), in the present paper both Mode I and Mixed-Mode (I+II) static bending behaviour of an edge-cracked nanobeam is analysed by using the above model. More precisely, the cracked nanobeam is modelled by using a modification of the classical cracked-beam theory, consisting in dividing the beam into two beam segments connected through a massless elastic rotational spring, located at the cracked section. The problem is investigated within the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory. This model promotes a discontinuity in the bend rotation angle, which

is proportional to the first-derivative of the displacement or, equivalently, to the second one.

The paper is organised in the following Sections. **Section 2** is dedicated to the model formulation of both intact and cracked nanobeams. In **Section 3**, the bending stiffness of the cracked cross-section is computed by exploiting: (i) the Griffith energy criterion, to derive the compliance of a cracked plate under bending as a function of the energy release rate, and (ii) the conventional Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics, to express the above rate as a function of the Stress-Intensity Factor. In such a context, a critical crack size at which the LEFM breakdown is defined. Cracks under both Mode I and Mixed-Mode (I+II) loading are considered. In **Section 4**, an edge-cracked cantilever nanobeam, subjected to a transversal point load at the free end, is analysed by the Stress-Driven nonlocal Model. The static deflection is calculated and discussed for different values of both relative crack depth, crack location and crack orientation. Conclusions are summarised in **Section 5**.

2. FORMULATION

2.1 Intact nanobeam with discontinuities

The formulation of the Stress-Driven nonlocal Model (SDM) for intact nanobeams with internal discontinuities under bending is here presented.

Let us consider the nanobeam as a straight beam with a length L , under a generic bending moment $M(x)$, with a discontinuity at the abscissa $x=x_d$ (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Schematisation of a nanobeam with an internal discontinuity in correspondence of $x=x_d$.

The beam is split in two parts: the first part (named *left part*), with abscissa $0 \leq x \leq x_d$, subjected to the bending moment $M_1(x)$, and the second part (named *right part*), with abscissa $x_d < x \leq L$, subjected to the bending moment $M_2(x)$.

The SDM governing equations, according to the differential formulation reported in Refs [37,38,40], are written for a Euler-Bernoulli nanobeam as:

$$\chi_1^{(2)}(x) - \frac{1}{L_c^2} \chi_1(x) = -\frac{1}{L_c^2} \frac{M_1(x)}{IE} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq x \leq x_d \quad (1a)$$

$$\chi_2^{(2)}(x) - \frac{1}{L_c^2} \chi_2(x) = -\frac{1}{L_c^2} \frac{M_2(x)}{IE} \quad \text{for } x_d < x \leq L \quad (1b)$$

where $\chi_1(x)$ and $\chi_2(x)$ are the curvatures of the *left* and *right parts* of the nanobeam, respectively. Moreover, E and I are the elastic modulus and the moment of inertia of the nanobeam, respectively, whereas L_c is the material internal characteristic length [41]. Two constitutive boundary conditions and two constitutive continuity conditions are added to the above governing equations [37, 38, 40].

However, it is in general more convenient to rewrite **Eqs (1)** in terms of the transversal displacement, $v(x)$, by exploiting the well-known relationship $\chi(x) = v^{(2)}(x)$, and by deriving **Eqs (1)** two times with respect to the axial coordinate x . Therefore, the differential governing equations become:

$$v_1^{(6)}(x) - \frac{1}{L_c^2} v_1^{(4)}(x) = -\frac{1}{L_c^2} \frac{M_1^{(2)}(x)}{IE} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq x \leq x_d \quad (2a)$$

$$v_2^{(6)}(x) - \frac{1}{L_c^2} v_2^{(4)}(x) = -\frac{1}{L_c^2} \frac{M_2^{(2)}(x)}{IE} \quad \text{for } x_d < x \leq L \quad (2b)$$

being $v_1(x)$ and $v_2(x)$ the transversal displacements of the *left* and *right parts* of the nanobeam, respectively. Therefore, the constitutive boundary and continuity conditions are the following ones:

- *Constitutive boundary conditions* (CBCs) at the beam ends ($x=0$ and $x=L$):

$$v_1^{(3)}(0) - \frac{1}{L_c} v_1^{(2)}(0) = 0 \quad (3a)$$

$$v_2^{(3)}(L) + \frac{1}{L_c} v_2^{(2)}(L) = 0 \quad (3b)$$

- *Constitutive Continuity Conditions* (CCCs) at the internal discontinuity ($x = x_d$) [37–39]:

$$v_1^{(3)}(x_d) + \frac{1}{L_c} v_1^{(2)}(x_d) = \frac{2}{L_c} \chi_{1,2}(x_d) \quad (4a)$$

$$v_2^{(3)}(x_d) - \frac{1}{L_c} v_2^{(2)}(x_d) = -\frac{2}{L_c} \chi_{2,1}(x_d) \quad (4b)$$

being

$$\chi_{1,2}(x) = \int_{x_d}^L \psi(x-t, L_c) \frac{M_2(t)}{IE} dt \quad (5a)$$

$$\chi_{2,1}(x) = \int_0^{x_d} \psi(t-x, L_c) \frac{M_1(t)}{IE} dt \quad (5b)$$

with $\psi(x-t, L_c)$ (or equivalently $\psi(t-x, L_c)$) the averaging special kernel depending on L_c [39].

By solving the above sixth-order differential equations, the general integral solution depends on twelve integration constants. Therefore, the solving system is obtained by imposing twelve boundary conditions, that is:

- (i) two CBCs given by **Eqs (3)**;
- (ii) two CCCs given by **Eqs (4)**;
- (iii) eight suitable kinematic/static boundary conditions at the nanobeam ends (that is, $x=0$ and $x=L$) and at the internal discontinuity (that is, $x=x_d$).

In order to prove the accuracy of the above nonlocal model, the results of the experimental tests reported in Ref. [42] are simulated. More precisely, Lam et al. [42] tested nanobeams cut from thin layers made of an epoxy polymer (**Figure 2(a)**). The height H of such nanobeams is much smaller than their length L and thickness B (the Authors' purpose was to neglect the beam deformation in the thickness direction). More precisely, four nanobeams were tested with different heights, that is, $H=20\mu\text{m}$, $38\mu\text{m}$, $75\mu\text{m}$ and $115\mu\text{m}$; the beam length is function of the height, that is, $L=10H$, whereas B was taken constant and equal to $235\mu\text{m}$.

The elastic behaviour of the nanobeams was characterised through uniaxial tension tests by using a mechanical tester. According to the results reported in Ref. [42], the elastic modulus E was independent of the nanobeam height and equal to about 1.5GPa .

The four nanobeams were subjected to bending tests by using a nano-loading system containing a load actuator with a load range between zero and 10mN , and a resolution of $10\mu\text{N}$. One end of each beam was adhesively mounted onto a glass substrate, whereas the other end was loaded by the above load actuator.

Figure 2. Experimental bending testing [42]: (a) schematisation of the epoxy polymeric cantilever nanobeam under bending loading and (b) comparison between the experimental and the numerical results.

The transversal beam displacement at $x=L$ and named deflection in the following (that is the displacement of the loading point in **Figure 2(a)**) was measured with a displacement resolution of $0.1nm$.

The experimental load vs deflection curves are plotted in **Figure 2(b)** (red dashed lines). Note that, the load-deflection curve related to the nanobeam with $H=75\mu m$ coincides with that related to the nanobeam with $H=115\mu m$.

Such experimental data are simulated through the nonlocal SDM, previously presented, by imposing suitable boundary conditions. More precisely, the beam transversal displacement, $v(x)$, is determined by employing **Eq. (2a)**, by assuming $v(x)=v_1(x)$, $M(x)=M_1(x)$ and $x_d=L$. Such an equation is used together with the CBCs of **Eqs (3)**, by assuming $v(x)=v_1(x)=v_2(x)$. Finally, four kinematic/static boundary conditions are added:

- *Kinematic boundary conditions* (KBCs) at $x=0$:

$$v(0)=0 \quad (6a)$$

$$v^{(1)}(0)=0 \quad (6b)$$

- *Static Boundary Conditions* (SBCs) at $x=L$:

$$v^{(4)}(L)-\frac{1}{L_c^2}v^{(2)}(L)=0 \quad (7a)$$

$$v^{(5)}(L)-\frac{1}{L_c^2}v^{(3)}(L)=\frac{F}{EI} \quad (7b)$$

The above six equation system is implemented in a Maple code and the obtained results in terms of load vs deflection are plotted in **Figure 2(b)** (black continuous lines). Note that, to solve the above equations, the material internal characteristic length L_c needs to be properly defined. To this aim, such a length is determined by calibrating the present nonlocal model through the experimental data (related to the nanobeam with $H=20\mu m$) and set L_c equal to $120\mu m$ (assumed constant for all the examined nanobeams).

By comparing the numerical results with the experimental ones, a good agreement can be observed. More in details:

- the best results are obtained for the nanobeam with $H=20\mu m$, for which the maximum error in estimating the deflection is equal to -4.3% , for a load equal to about $328\mu N$;
- the maximum error in estimating the deflection of the nanobeam with $H=38\mu m$, is equal to $+6.1\%$, for a load equal to about $260\mu N$;
- the worst results are obtained for the nanobeam with $H=75\mu m$, for which the maximum error in estimating the deflection is equal to -21.1% , for a load equal to about $152\mu N$;
- the maximum error in estimating the deflection of the nanobeam with $H=115\mu m$, is equal to -13.5% , for a load equal to about $152\mu N$.

2.2 Edge-cracked nanobeam

As far as the problem of an edge-cracked nanobeam under bending is concerned, the SDM formulation for intact nanobeams with internal discontinuities, presented in the previous Sub-Section, can be employed by properly defining the internal continuity conditions in correspondence of $x=x_d$.

Let us consider a Euler-Bernuolli nanobeam under bending loading, having length L , thickness B , height H and containing a crack of length a located at a distance L_1 from the left end of the beam, as shown in **Figure 3(a)**. The crack is assumed to be oriented of an angle θ with respect to the vertical direction (that is, the direction orthogonal to the beam axis) and it always remains open during loading.

The problem of the cracked nanobeam under bending can be modelled through a modification of the classical cracked-beam theory, by considering two beam segments (having a length of L_1 and of $L-L_1$, respectively), connected through a massless elastic rotational spring located at the cracked section, characterised by a stiffness K (**Figure 3(b)**). Such a stiffness represents the bending stiffness of the cracked section [1,35].

Figure 3. Edge-cracked nanobeam: (a) schematisation and (b) model with a massless elastic rotational spring.

The transversal displacement of the cracked nanobeam can then be determined by using the governing equations (see **Eqs (2)**), together with the CBCs (see **Eqs (3)**) and the CCCs (see **Eqs (4)**) presented in the previous Sub-Section, and by imposing $x_d=L_1$ (that is, the section of the internal discontinuity coincides with the cracked section).

For a beam under bending, further four continuity conditions (both kinematic and static) can be imposed at $x=L_1$, that is, at the cracked section modelled as an elastic spring, and more precisely:

$$v_1(L_1)=v_2(L_1) \quad (8a)$$

$$v_2^{(1)}(L_1)-v_1^{(1)}(L_1)=\left[v_1^{(2)}(L_1)-L_c^2 \cdot v_1^{(4)}(L_1)\right] \frac{EI}{K}=\frac{M_1(L_1)}{K} \quad (8b)$$

$$v_1^{(4)}(L_1)-\frac{1}{L_c^2} v_1^{(2)}(L_1)=v_2^{(4)}(L_1)-\frac{1}{L_c^2} v_2^{(2)}(L_1) \quad (8c)$$

$$v_1^{(5)}(L_1)-\frac{1}{L_c^2} v_1^{(3)}(L_1)=v_2^{(5)}(L_1)-\frac{1}{L_c^2} v_2^{(3)}(L_1) \quad (8d)$$

It is worth noting that **Eq. (8b)** describes the jump in the nanobeam rotation in correspondence of the cracked section **[1,35]**. Details on the computation of K are presented in the following Section.

Finally, other four boundary conditions at the beam ends (both kinematic and static) are required to obtain a unique solution of the elastic problem of the cracked nanobeam.

3. STIFFNESS OF NANOBEAM AT CRACK LOCATION

The stiffness of the nanobeam at crack location is computed by exploiting: (i) the Griffith energy criterion, to derive the compliance, c , of a cracked plate under bending, as a function of the energy release rate, G , and (ii) the conventional Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM), to express G as a function of the Stress-Intensity Factor (SIF).

It is worth noticing that it was proved that in the cracked nanostructures there is no stress singularity at the crack tip **[24, 43-45]**, although stress still varies with a square root singularity in the region near the crack tip **[24, 43-45]**, being this last trend similar to that occurring in the K-dominance region according to LEFM. However, when the sizes of the material are scaled down to nanometers, the above region is limited to nanometers too. That is, an extremely low number of atoms are present in the region.

Therefore, it makes sense to ask if, into the region characterised by a square root singularity, the SIF, within the framework of the continuum theory, is still valid to describe brittle fracture, being possible to be violated the LEFM continuum assumption that postulated the presence of a large number of atoms in the vicinity of the crack tip. Consequently, a critical crack size at which the LEFM breakdown, that is, a dimension below which brittle fracture is characterised by discrete events at atomic scale (i.e. series of atomic bonds breaking) different from continuum description, needs to be defined.

3.1 LEFM breakdown: definition of the critical crack size

In order to define the critical crack size at which the LEFM breakdown, let us consider the numerical investigation performed by Shimada et al. **[44,45]**, and hereafter summarised.

3.1.1 Description of the atomistic simulations

The Authors considered two types of cracked specimen, and more precisely: a central cracked plate with a width of $2W$ under tension (crack length equal to $2a$), and an edge cracked plate with a width of W under bending (crack length equal to a). The specimens consisted of a single crystal of a silicon diamond-cubic structure. Several tens of numerical models were employed, by varying the geometrical parameter W from 1.1nm to 138nm, and consequently the parameter, a , being defined as $a=W/3$.

The brittle nature of fracture at the crack tip was described by a bond-order potential of the Stillinger-Weber form **[46]**, and classical atomic simulations were performed, where the first-principles density-functional theory was applied for crack propagation by using the supercell set-up **[47]**.

The simulations were performed up to the critical loading, that is, when the crack propagation became mechanically unstable, with the crack propagating along the material cleavage plane.

The numerical results were analysed by the Authors from a continuum mechanics perspective, by assuming each specimen to be an elastic medium.

The fracture toughness for the bulk material was $1.03\text{MPa}\sqrt{m}$. At the nanoscale, it was observed a perfect agreement of fracture toughness with the bulk one for large specimens, whereas a deviation from the bulk one was noted for small specimens. The size of the region (assumed with a circular shape) characterised by a square root singularity, in terms of the distance from the crack tip, Λ_K , was measured for each specimen and plotted against the corresponding fracture toughness value. The Authors observed that a critical size for Λ_K existed, below which brittle fracture was no longer governed by the SIF within the framework of the continuum theory, and equal to about 2÷3nm.

3.1.2 Results re-interpretation and critical crack size calculation

In Refs [44,45], the sizes of $\Lambda_K = 5.1\text{nm}$ and 4.1nm are reported for tensile and bending loading, respectively, for large specimens, that is when $W = 104\text{nm}$ ($a = 34.7\text{nm}$), and $\Lambda_K = 0.8\text{nm}$, for both loading conditions, for small specimens, that is when $W = 16\text{nm}$ ($a = 5.3\text{nm}$).

By computing the ratio between the crack length over $\Lambda_K/2$, it ranges between 13.33 and 27.22, in agreement, in terms of order of magnitude, with both the statement reported by: (i) Pook in Ref. [48], which claims that the SIF provides a reasonable description of the crack tip stress field in a K-dominance region defined by a radius $\Lambda_K/2$ equal to the crack length over 10; (ii) Pippan et al. in Ref. [49], which claims that $\Lambda_K/2$ varies between the crack length over 5 and the ligament width.

Figure 4. Determination of the critical crack size defining the LEFM breakdown [48].

Therefore, by assuming such a ratio equal to 10 and re-interpreting the results reported in Refs [44,45], a critical crack size, below which the LEFM breakdown, may be defined equal to $10\div 15\text{nm}$ as it is reported in **Figure 4**. Moreover, such a result is in good agreement with that by Zhang et al. [50], where the Authors experimentally and numerically found a critical crack size equal to about 10nm for graphene sheets under tension [51].

Therefore, the main assumption adopted in the present paper to compute the stiffness of nanobeam at the crack location is that the crack length is greater than the above critical crack size and, in favour of safety, cracks with a length greater than 100nm are considered in the following.

3.2 Stiffness computation

Let us consider a cracked plate (crack length equal to a) of thickness B under a bending M , with the end faces free to move during crack extension. Under the action of the load, the load application faces undergo a relative rotation φ . When the crack increases in depth by an amount da , the rotation increases by an amount $d\varphi$, and the work done by the external forces is equal to $M \cdot d\varphi$. It follows that the energy release rate, G , is given by:

$$G = \frac{d}{da}(F - U) = \frac{1}{B} \left(M \frac{d\varphi}{da} - \frac{dU_t}{da} \right) \quad (9)$$

where F is the work done by the external forces per unit thickness, and U_t is the total elastic energy in the plate, being $U = U_t/B$.

Being the deformation elastic, as long as there is no crack growth, the rotation φ is proportional to the load, that is $\varphi = cM$, where c is the compliance of the plate and $U_t = \frac{1}{2}M\varphi = \frac{1}{2}cM^2$. Therefore, **Eq. (9)** yields to:

$$G = \frac{1}{B} \left(M \cdot c \frac{dM}{da} + M^2 \frac{dc}{da} - \frac{1}{2} M^2 \frac{dc}{da} - \frac{1}{2} c (2M) \frac{dM}{da} \right) \quad (10)$$

and by deleting the terms containing dM/da , G is given by:

$$G = \frac{M^2}{2B} \frac{dc}{da} = -\frac{1}{B} \frac{dU_t}{da} \quad (11)$$

3.2.1 Crack under Mode I loading

For a crack under pure Mode I loading, **Eq. (11)** can be rewritten according to Irwin's relationship under plane strain condition as [52]:

$$\frac{K_I^2}{E} (1 - \nu^2) = \frac{M^2}{2B} \frac{dc}{da} \quad (12)$$

where ν is the Poisson's coefficient, and K_I is the Mode I SIF.

For an isotropic beam with rectangular cross-section under bending, containing an open edge crack with length a , the analytical solution, along with the expression of SIF, is given by Gross et al. [53]:

$$K_I = \frac{6M}{BH^2} \sqrt{\pi a} f\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) \quad (13)$$

where:

$$f\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) = 1.122 - 1.40\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) + 7.33\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^2 - 13.08\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^3 + 14.0\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^4 \quad (14)$$

Other solutions for the SIF are available in the literature and may be alternatively employed [54].

It is worth noticing that, in the context of nanobeams, **Eqs (13)** and **(14)** hold under the assumption presented in **Section 3.1.2**, that is, the crack length a is greater than a critical crack size, quantified equal to 100nm, in favour of safety.

After substituting **Eqs (13)** and **(14)** in **Eq. (12)**, the compliance of the beam in correspondence of the cracked cross-section is given by:

$$c = \frac{72\pi(1-\nu^2)}{BH^4E} \int_0^a y f^2 dy = \frac{72\pi(1-\nu^2)}{BH^2E} F(\xi) \quad (15)$$

where $F(\xi)$ represents the shape correction function, and it is given by:

$$F(\xi) = \int_0^\xi z f^2 dz \quad (16)$$

being $\xi = a/H$.

Therefore, the stiffness of a nanobeam under Mode I static bending moment in correspondence to the cracked cross-section is given by $K = 1/c$ (to be implemented in **Eq. (8b)**).

3.2.2 Crack under Mixed-Mode (I+II) loading

For a crack under both Mode I and Mode II loading, **Eq. (12)** can be rewritten according to the Irwin's relationship and by exploiting the superposition principle under plane strain condition:

$$\frac{K_I^2 + K_{II}^2}{E} (1-\nu^2) = \frac{M^2}{2B} \frac{dc}{da} \quad (17)$$

where K_{II} is the Mode II SIF.

For an isotropic beam with a rectangular cross-section under bending, containing an inclined open edge crack with a length a , the expression of SIFs were given by Wilson [55] in a graphical form for $\theta = 22.5^\circ$ and 45.0° , being θ the angle formed by the crack with the direction perpendicular to the beam axis. By interpolating such curves with polynomials, the following equations are obtained for $\theta = 22.5^\circ$:

$$K_I = \frac{6M}{BH^2} f_I\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) \quad (18)$$

with:

$$f_I\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) = 0.97 - 0.68\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) + 2.52\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^2 + 0.23\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^3 \quad (19)$$

and:

$$K_{II} = \frac{6M}{BH^2} f_{II}\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) \quad (20)$$

with:

$$f_{II}\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) = 0.20 + 0.19\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) - 0.62\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^2 + 0.82\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^3 \quad (21)$$

For $\theta = 45.0^\circ$, the following equations for f_I and f_{II} are obtained:

$$f_I\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) = 0.82 - 0.98\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) + 2.13\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^2 - 0.45\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^3 \quad (22)$$

$$f_{II}\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) = 0.32 - 0.04\left(\frac{a}{H}\right) - 0.09\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^2 + 0.43\left(\frac{a}{H}\right)^3 \quad (23)$$

The compliance of the beam in correspondence to the cracked cross-section is given by:

$$c = \frac{72\pi(1-\nu^2)}{BH^4E} \int_0^a y (f_I^2 + f_{II}^2) dy = \frac{72\pi(1-\nu^2)}{BH^2E} [F_I(\xi) + F_{II}(\xi)] \quad (24)$$

with:

$$F_I(\xi) = \int_0^\xi z f_I^2 dz \quad (25)$$

and:

$$F_{II}(\xi) = \int_0^\xi z f_{II}^2 dz \quad (26)$$

4. EDGE-CRACKED CANTILEVER NANOBEAM

The problem of an edge-cracked nanocantilever beam under bending is analysed in the following by performing a parametric study on the effect of three parameters related to the crack configuration, that is: the crack length a , the crack location L_1 and the crack orientation θ . More precisely, it is investigated:

(i) the influence of the crack severity, by varying the relative crack depth, $\xi = a/H$;

(ii) the influence of the crack location, by varying the ratio $\eta = L_1/L$;

(iii) the influence of the crack orientation, by varying the angle θ .

4.1 Governing equations

The edge-cracked cantilever nanobeam is constrained at the *left* end ($x=0$), whereas a concentrated force F is applied at the free (*right*) end ($x=L$).

The nanobeam transversal displacement is computed by using the governing equations of **Eqs (2)** together with the CBCs given by **Eqs (3)**, the CCCs given by **Eqs (4)** and the internal conditions given by **Eqs (8)**. Finally, the kinematic and static boundary conditions given by **Eqs (6)** and **(7)** are imposed. The abovementioned equations are implemented in a Maple code. The system of twelve equations in twelve unknowns is solved and the expression of the equations describing the nanobeam transversal displacement can be determined.

4.2 Numerical results and discussion

The results of the parametric study are presented and discussed in the following. The examined nanobeam is made of an aluminium, having elastic modulus and Poisson's coefficient equal to $E=70GPa$ and $\nu=0.33$, respectively [35]. The material internal characteristic length is assumed equal to $L_c=15\mu m$, which is a size consistent with the average grain size of an aluminium. The applied load F at the free end is assumed equal to $F=10\mu N$ for all the analyses.

4.2.1 Influence of crack severity

In order to investigate the effect of the crack severity (by varying the relative crack depth $\xi=a/H$), the dimensionless deflection, that is, $v_2(L)/H$, computed according to both the present *nonlocal SDM* and the *classical beam theory*, is listed in **Table 1** for three values of relative crack depth (that is, $\xi=0.1, 0.5$ and 0.8) and for different values of the dimensionless characteristic length, $\lambda=L_c/L$. The case of intact beam ($\xi=0.0$) is also considered. Regarding the beam geometry, crack location and orientation, the following assumptions are made: $L/H=20$, $B=H$, $\eta=L_1/L=0.01$ and $\theta=0.0^\circ$.

Table 1. Dimensionless deflection of the edge-cracked nanobeam for different relative crack depth values, $\xi=a/H$, and dimensionless characteristic lengths, $\lambda=L_c/L$, being $L/H=20$, $B=H$, $\eta=L_1/L=0.01$ and $F=10\mu N$.

λ	Stress Driven nonlocal Model				Classical continuum theory			
	Intact	$\xi=0.1$	$\xi=0.5$	$\xi=0.8$	Intact	$\xi=0.1$	$\xi=0.5$	$\xi=0.8$
0.5	0.960503	0.988776	1.889361	8.079615	2.031746	2.060018	2.960604	9.150858
0.4	0.698061	0.716123	1.292541	5.254405	1.300317	1.318380	1.894798	5.856662
0.3	0.452373	0.462533	0.786752	3.015262	0.731429	0.741588	1.065808	3.294318
0.2	0.235042	0.280197	0.383658	1.374075	0.325079	0.370234	0.473695	1.464112
0.1	0.069323	0.070452	0.106477	0.354098	0.081270	0.082399	0.118423	0.366045
0.01	0.000801	0.000812	0.001172	0.003648	0.000813	0.000824	0.001184	0.003660
0.005	0.000202	0.000204	0.000295	0.000914	0.000203	0.000206	0.000297	0.000915
0.001	0.000008	0.000008	0.000012	0.000037	0.000008	0.000008	0.000012	0.000037

As can be observed, the deflection decreases by decreasing the value of λ for a given value of ξ , whereas, for a given value of λ , the deflection increases by increasing ξ , as expected, since by increasing the crack severity the beam becomes more flexible. Moreover, for the

same crack configuration, the nanobeam is stiffer than the macrobeam, although the difference between local and nonlocal deflections decreases considerably by increasing the crack depth. Further, such a difference is smaller than 1.5% for $\lambda \leq 0.01$ and for all the values of ξ examined.

The influence of the crack severity can be well recognised in **Figure 5**, where the deflection obtained from both *nonlocal SDM* and *local classical beam theory* is plotted against the relative crack depth, ξ , for four values of the dimensionless characteristic length (that is, $\lambda = 0.001, 0.01, 0.10$ and 0.50).

As can be observed, with the increase of the crack severity, the difference between local and nonlocal results slightly decreases. Moreover, such a difference is appreciable for $\lambda \geq 0.1$.

In **Figure 6**, the effect of the beam length-to-height ratio, L/H , (beam slenderness) on the deflection is analysed by varying the crack severity. In particular, four values of the above ratio ($L/H = 5, 10, 15$ and 20) and four values of the dimensionless characteristic length ($\lambda = 0.001, 0.01, 0.10$ and 0.50) are considered. Moreover, it is assumed $B = H$, $\eta = 0.01$ and $\theta = 0.0^\circ$.

As can be noted, with the increase of the ratio L/H , the influence of the crack severity becomes more pronounced. This is because by increasing the beam slenderness, the nanobeam becomes more flexible and more sensitive to the crack depth. By considering the different dimensionless characteristic length values showed in **Figure 6**, it can be remarked that, although the value of the deflection is very different (some orders of magnitude) by varying λ , the trends of the curves are quite similar and that, consequently, the effect of the slenderness is quite similar for all nanobeams examined.

Finally, in **Figure 7**, the dimensionless transversal vertical displacement is plotted against the dimensionless axial coordinate x/L for the four dimensionless characteristic length values ($\lambda = 0.001, 0.01, 0.10$ and 0.50) and three values of the relative crack depth (that is, $\xi = 0.1, 0.5$ and 0.8). Regarding the beam geometry, crack location and orientation, the following assumptions are made: $L/H = 20$, $B = H$, $\eta = 0.01$ and $\theta = 0.0^\circ$.

It is worth noting that the deflection increases with the increase of the relative crack depth, as expected, for all the λ values examined, due to the increase of the beam flexibility. By considering the different dimensionless characteristic length values showed in **Figure 7**, it can be remarked that the trends of the curves are quite similar, although the influence of the crack severity is more pronounced in the case of nanobeam ($\lambda = 0.50$), as highlighted also by the numerical data reported in **Table 1**.

Figure 5. Dimensionless deflection against the relative crack depth, ξ , according to both the *nonlocal SDM* and the *continuum theory*, for: (a) $\lambda=0.001$, (b) $\lambda=0.01$, (c) $\lambda=0.10$ and (d) $\lambda=0.50$ ($L/H=20$, $B=H$, $\eta=0.01$ and $F=10\mu N$).

Figure 6. Dimensionless deflection against the relative crack depth, ξ , according to the *nonlocal SDM*, for different values of L/H and: (a) $\lambda=0.001$, (b) $\lambda=0.01$, (c) $\lambda=0.10$ and (d) $\lambda=0.50$ ($B=H$, $\eta=0.01$ and $F=10\mu N$).

Figure 7. Dimensionless transversal displacement against the dimensionless axial coordinate, according to the *nonlocal SDM*, for three values of the relative crack depth ($\xi = 0.1, 0.5$ and 0.8) and: (a) $\lambda = 0.001$, (b) $\lambda = 0.01$, (c) $\lambda = 0.10$ and (d) $\lambda = 0.50$ ($L/H = 20$, $B = H$, $\eta = 0.01$ and $F = 10\mu N$).

4.2.2 Influence of crack location

In order to investigate the effect of the crack location (by varying the ratio $\eta=L_1/L$), the dimensionless deflection, computed according to both the present *nonlocal SDM* and the *classical beam theory*, is listed in **Table 2** for different values of the dimensionless characteristic length, $\lambda=L_c/L$, and three values of crack location (that is, $\eta=0.01, 0.3$ and 0.5).

Table 2. Dimensionless deflection of the edge-cracked nanobeam for different crack locations, $\eta=L_1/L$, and dimensionless characteristic lengths, $\lambda=L_c/L$, being $L/H=20, B=H, \xi=0.8$ and $F=10\mu N$.

λ	Stress Driven nonlocal Model				Classical continuum theory			
	Intact	$\eta=0.01$	$\eta=0.3$	$\eta=0.5$	Intact	$\eta=0.01$	$\eta=0.3$	$\eta=0.5$
0.5	0.960503	8.079874	4.519826	2.776484	2.031746	9.151116	5.591068	3.847727
0.4	0.698061	5.254405	2.976001	1.860275	1.300317	5.856662	3.578257	2.462532
0.3	0.452373	3.015262	1.733687	1.106104	0.731429	3.294318	2.012742	1.385160
0.2	0.235042	1.374075	0.804500	0.525582	0.325079	1.464112	0.894538	0.615619
0.1	0.069323	0.354098	0.211696	0.141962	0.081270	0.366045	0.223643	0.153909
0.01	0.000801	0.003648	0.002224	0.001527	0.000813	0.003660	0.002236	0.001539
0.005	0.000202	0.000914	0.000558	0.000383	0.000203	0.000915	0.000559	0.000385
0.001	0.000008	0.000037	0.000022	0.000015	0.000008	0.000037	0.000022	0.000015

The case of intact beam ($\xi=0.0$) is also considered. Regarding the beam geometry, relative crack depth and crack orientation, the following assumptions are made: $L/H=20, B=H, \xi=0.8$ and $\theta=0.0^\circ$.

As can be observed, the deflection decreases by both decreasing λ for a given value of η , and increasing η for a given value of λ , as expected. Moreover, it can be noted that, for the same crack configuration, the nanobeam is stiffer than the macrobeam, although the difference between local and nonlocal deflections decreases for low values of η . Further, such a difference is smaller than 1.0% for $\lambda \leq 0.01$ and for all the crack locations considered.

The influence of the crack location can be well-observed in **Figure 8**, where the deflection obtained from both the *nonlocal SDM* and the *local classical beam theory* is plotted against the crack location, η , for four values of the dimensionless characteristic length (that is, $\lambda=0.001, 0.01, 0.10$ and 0.50).

As can be observed, with the increase of the crack location values, the difference between the local and nonlocal results slightly increases. Moreover, such a difference is appreciable for $\lambda \geq 0.1$.

In **Figure 9**, the effect of the beam length-to-height ratio, L/H , (beam slenderness) on the deflection is analysed by varying the crack location. In particular, four values of the above ratio ($L/H=5, 10, 15$ and 20) and four values of the dimensionless characteristic length ($\lambda=0.001, 0.01, 0.10$ and 0.50) are considered. Moreover, it is assumed $B=H, \xi=0.8$ and $\theta=0.0^\circ$.

Figure 8. Dimensionless deflection against the crack location, η , according to both the *nonlocal SDM* and the *continuum theory*, for: (a) $\lambda=0.001$, (b) $\lambda=0.01$, (c) $\lambda=0.10$ and (d) $\lambda=0.50$ ($L/H=20$, $B=H$, $\xi=0.8$ and $F=10\mu N$).

Figure 9. Dimensionless deflection against the crack location, η , according to the *nonlocal SDM*, for different values of L/H and: (a) $\lambda=0.001$, (b) $\lambda=0.01$, (c) $\lambda=0.10$ and (d) $\lambda=0.50$ ($B=H$, $\xi=0.8$ and $F=10\mu N$).

Figure 10. Dimensionless transversal displacement against the dimensionless axial coordinate, according to the *nonlocal SDM*, for three values of the crack location ($\eta=0.01, 0.3$ and 0.5) and: (a) $\lambda=0.001$, (b) $\lambda=0.01$, (c) $\lambda=0.10$ and (d) $\lambda=0.50$ ($L/H=20$, $B=H$, $\xi=0.8$ and $F=10\mu N$).

As can be noted, with the increase of the ratio L/H , the influence of the crack location becomes more pronounced. This is because by increasing the beam slenderness (that is, by increasing L/H), the

nanobeam becomes more flexible and more sensitive to the crack position. By increasing η from 0.01 to 0.9, the deflection decreases of about 92.4%, 86.6%, 81.5% and 77.0% for $L/H=5, 10, 15$ and 20 , respectively, when λ is equal to 0.001 (macrobeam) and of about 95.8%, 92.7%, 89.9% and 87.2% for $L/H=5, 10, 15$ and 20 , respectively, when λ is equal to 0.50 (nanobeam).

Finally, in **Figure 10**, the dimensionless transversal vertical displacement is plotted against the dimensionless axial coordinate x/L for the four dimensionless characteristic length values ($\lambda=0.001, 0.01, 0.10$ and 0.50) and three values of the crack location (that is, $\eta=0.01, 0.3$ and 0.5). Regarding the beam geometry, relative crack depth and crack orientation, the following assumptions are made: $L/H=20$, $B=H$, $\xi=0.8$ and $\theta=0.0^\circ$. It is worth noting that the transversal vertical displacement decreases with the increase of the crack location ratio values, as expected, for all the λ values due to the reduction of the beam flexibility, since the crack is more distant from the constrained end of the beam.

By considering the different dimensionless characteristic length values showed in **Figure 10**, it can be remarked that the trends of the curves are quite similar, although the influence of the crack location is more pronounced in the case of nanobeam ($\lambda=0.50$), as also highlighted by the numerical data reported in **Table 2**.

4.2.3 Influence of crack orientation

Finally, in the present Sub-Section, the effect of the crack orientation (by varying the angle θ) is investigated. The dimensionless deflection, computed according to both the present *nonlocal SDM* and the *classical beam theory*, is listed in **Table 3** for different values of the dimensionless characteristic length, $\lambda=L_c/L$, and three crack orientations (that is, $\theta=0.0^\circ, 22.5^\circ$ and 45.0°). The case of intact beam ($\xi=0.0$) is also considered. Regarding the beam geometry, relative crack depth and crack location, the following assumptions are made: $L/H=20$, $B=H$, $\xi=0.8$ and $\eta=0.3$.

Table 3. Dimensionless deflection of the edge-cracked nanobeam for different crack orientations, θ , and dimensionless characteristic lengths, $\lambda=L_c/L$, being $L/H=20$, $B=H$, $\xi=0.8$, $\eta=0.3$ and $F=10\mu N$.

λ	Stress Driven nonlocal Model				Classical continuum theory			
	Intact	$\theta=0.0^\circ$	$\theta=22.5^\circ$	$\theta=45.0^\circ$	Intact	$\theta=0.0^\circ$	$\theta=22.5^\circ$	$\theta=45.0^\circ$
0.5	0.960503	4.519826	2.828475	1.715647	2.031746	5.591068	3.899717	2.786889
0.4	0.698061	2.976001	1.893533	1.181359	1.300317	3.578257	2.495789	1.783616
0.3	0.452373	1.733687	1.124831	0.724233	0.731429	2.012742	1.403887	1.003288
0.2	0.235042	0.804500	0.533908	0.355867	0.325079	0.881527	0.623945	0.445904
0.1	0.069323	0.020857	0.144041	0.099529	0.081270	0.022364	0.155988	0.111476
0.01	0.000801	0.002224	0.001548	0.001103	0.000813	0.002236	0.001560	0.001115
0.005	0.000202	0.000558	0.000385	0.000277	0.000203	0.000559	0.000387	0.000279
0.001	0.000008	0.000022	0.000016	0.000011	0.000008	0.000022	0.000016	0.000011

Figure 11. Dimensionless transversal displacement against the dimensionless axial coordinate, according to the *nonlocal SDM*, for three values of the crack orientation ($\theta = 0.0^\circ, 22.5^\circ$ and 45.0°) and: (a) $\lambda = 0.001$, (b) $\lambda = 0.01$, (c) $\lambda = 0.10$ and (d) $\lambda = 0.50$ ($L/H = 20$, $B = H$, $\xi = 0.8$, $\eta = 0.3$ and $F = 10\mu N$).

As can be observed, the deflection decreases by both decreasing λ for a given value of θ , and increasing θ for a given value of λ , as

expected. Moreover, it can be noted that, for the same crack configuration, the nanobeam is stiffer than the macrobeam, and that the difference between local and nonlocal deflections increases by increasing the value of the angle. Further, such a difference is smaller than 1.1% for $\lambda \leq 0.01$, for all the crack orientations considered.

Finally, in **Figure 11**, the dimensionless transversal vertical displacement is plotted against the dimensionless axial coordinate x/L for the four dimensionless characteristic length values ($\lambda = 0.001, 0.01, 0.10$ and 0.50) and three values of the crack orientation (that is, $\theta = 0.0^\circ, 22.5^\circ$ and 45.0°). Regarding the beam geometry, relative crack depth and crack location, the following assumptions are made: $L/H = 20$, $B = H$, $\xi = 0.8$ and $\eta = 0.3$.

It is worth noting that with the increase of the crack orientation angle, the deflection decreases, as expected, for all the λ values, due to the reduction of the beam flexibility since the crack is not perpendicular to the beam axis. By considering the different dimensionless characteristic length values showed in **Figure 11**, it can be remarked that the trends of the curves are quite similar, although the influence of the crack orientation is more pronounced in the case of nanobeam ($\lambda = 0.50$), as also highlighted by the numerical data reported in **Table 3**.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the Mode I and Mixed-Mode (I+II) static bending behaviour of an edge-cracked nanobeam has been analysed by using the Stress-Driven nonlocal Model (SDM), where such a model has been applied for the first time for the case of Mixed-Mode loading. More precisely, the cracked nanobeam has been modelled by using a modification of the classical cracked-beam theory, consisting in dividing the beam into two beam segments connected through a massless elastic rotational spring located at the cracked section. The problem has been investigated within the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory. The bending stiffness of the cracked cross-section has been computed by exploiting: (i) the Griffith energy criterion, to derive the compliance of a cracked plate under bending as a function of the energy release rate, and (ii) the conventional Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics, to express the above rate as a function of the Stress-Intensity Factor. In such a context, a critical crack size at which the LEFM breakdown (that is, a dimension below which brittle fracture is characterised by discrete events at atomic scale different from continuum description) has been defined and taken equal to 100nm, in favour of safety.

Cracks under both Mode I and Mixed-Mode (I+II) loading have been considered. A case study of an edge-cracked cantilever nanobeam, subjected to a transversal point load at the free end, has been analysed by means of the Stress-Driven nonlocal Model. A parametric study on the effect of three parameters related to the crack configuration (that is, the crack length a , location L_1 and orientation θ) has been performed, by investigating the influence of: (i) the crack severity (by varying the relative crack depth $\xi = a/H$); (ii) the

crack location (by varying the ratio $\eta=L_1/L$); (iii) the crack orientation (by varying the angle θ). Moreover, a comparison between the local and the nonlocal results has been carried out by highlighting the higher stiffness of the cracked nanobeam with respect to the cracked macrobeam. Also, the effect of the beam slenderness (by varying the ratio L/H) has been investigated by observing that, in general, such an effect is slightly more pronounced for nanobeam ($\lambda=0.50$) than macrobeam ($\lambda=0.001$).

In conclusions, it can be stated that the modified classical cracked-beam theory (where the massless spring stiffness calculation is based on LEFM concepts) in conjunction with the Stress-Driven nonlocal Model can be a useful tool to analyse the Mixed-Mode (I+II) behaviour of edge-cracked nanobeams under static loading.

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Data availability

The raw data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time as the data also forms part of an ongoing study.

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NOMENCLATURE

a	crack length
B, H	nanobeam thickness and height, respectively
c	compliance of the nanobeam cracked cross-section
E	elastic modulus
G	energy release rate
I	inertia moment
K	stiffness of the massless elastic rotational spring
K_I, K_{II}	Mode I and Mode II Stress Intensity Factors, respectively
L	nanobeam length
L_1	distance of the edge-crack from the nanobeam left end
L_c	material internal characteristic length
L/H	beam slenderness
$M(x)$	bending moment
$M_1(x), M_2(x)$	bending moments acting on <i>left</i> and <i>right parts</i> of the nanobeam, respectively
$v(x)$	nanobeam transversal displacement
$v_1(x), v_2(x)$	transversal displacements of the <i>left</i> and <i>right parts</i> of the nanobeam, respectively
x_d	internal discontinuity axial coordinate
Λ_K	diameter of the circular-shape region characterised by a square root singularity of the SIF
$\eta = L_1/L$	relative crack location
θ	crack orientation angle
$\lambda = L_c/L$	dimensionless characteristic length
ν	Poisson's coefficient
$\xi = a/H$	relative crack depth
$\chi_1(x), \chi_2(x)$	curvatures of the <i>left</i> and <i>right parts</i> of the beam, respectively
$\psi(x-t, L_c)$	averaging special kernel depending on L_c